

Instructional Materials Organisation, Utilisation And Evaluation For Students' Academic Achievement In Public Secondary Schools In Abia State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined instructional materials organization, utilization and evaluation for students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State. Three (3) objectives with corresponding research questions and hypotheses guided the study. The study design was a descriptive survey with a population of 2,074 teachers distributed across the 252 public senior secondary schools in Abia State, from which 335 (16%) were selected as the sample, using stratified random sampling. Respondents responded to a validated 30 item instrument titled: Instructional Materials Organisation, Utilisation and Evaluation for Students' Academic Achievement Questionnaire (IMOUESAAQ), designed by the researcher in line with the modified 4-points Likert scale model of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) with a reliability index of 0.81, obtained using Cronbach Alpha statistics. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions, while the z-test was used in testing the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The study's findings showed that instructional materials are organised, utilised, and evaluated to support students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State. While acquisition practices varied significantly between urban and rural schools, no significant gender-based differences were observed across all dimensions. Hence, the study concluded that effective organisation, utilisation, and evaluation of instructional materials significantly contribute to students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State, while gender differences among teachers showed no significant impact. Consequently, it was recommended among others that the Ministry of Education should develop and enforce a uniform system for organising instructional materials in schools to improve accessibility and instructional efficiency.

Keywords: Instructional Materials, Organisation, Utilisation, Evaluation, Students, Academic Achievement

INTRODUCTION

Education is widely regarded as a powerful tool for driving national development, economic growth, and individual transformation. It enriches people's understanding of themselves and the world, improves the quality of life, and promotes social progress. In developing nations such as Nigeria, education is seen as a major vehicle for manpower development and national advancement, hence the high demand for the attainment of educational goals at all levels of government. The concept of education, derived from the Latin words educare (to bring up) and educere (to bring forth), has been interpreted from various

perspectives: sociologically as cultural transmission, historically as accumulated experience shaping the future, and psychologically as knowledge that influences behaviour. It is therefore regarded as an instrument par excellence for developing human intellect, technical competence, character, and effective citizenship for national development (FRN, 2014).

Consequently, academic achievement has become the central focus of the education system, as the success of schools and future opportunities of learners are often measured by the extent to which students attain educational goals, usually reflected in examination scores and continuous assessment outcomes (Anshu & Bilkees, 2022). Students' academic achievement refers to the extent to which learners attain their educational goals as measured through tests, examinations, and continuous assessments. It reflects the knowledge, skills, and competencies students acquire over a period of learning. It is often used as an indicator of the effectiveness of teaching, learning resources, and the overall school system (Fashiku & Yusuf, 2019).

Furthermore, students' academic achievement depends on several school-related factors, particularly the availability and effective management of instructional materials. These materials, such as textbooks, laboratory equipment, visual aids, and digital tools, support teaching, clarify concepts, and enhance learner engagement (Obi & Ogbuagu, 2020). Their management involves careful planning, acquisition, organisation, utilisation, maintenance, and evaluation to ensure they effectively support instructional delivery (Fashiku & Yusuf, 2019; Johnson, 2021). However, the focus of this study would be on organisation, utilisation and evaluation.

Organising instructional materials refers to the systematic arrangement and proper structuring of teaching resources to ensure easy access and alignment with lesson objectives. Also, utilising instructional materials involves the effective and purposeful use of these resources by teachers to enhance understanding, stimulate learners' interest, and improve classroom interaction, while evaluating instructional materials involves the continuous assessment of their relevance, adequacy, and effectiveness in achieving desired learning outcomes. Together, organization, utilization, and evaluation ensure that instructional materials are efficiently managed to support meaningful teaching and improve students' academic achievement (Obi & Ogbuagu, 2020).

Nevertheless, when well organised and properly utilised, instructional materials improve clarity, motivation, and knowledge retention among students (Ahmed & Yusuf, 2022; Alabi & Bello, 2023). Continuous evaluation further ensures that such resources remain relevant, accurate, and aligned with curriculum objectives, thereby improving learning outcomes (Okeke & Nwafor, 2023). However, despite increased government investment in educational resources, many public secondary schools appear not to fully benefit due to poor management of instructional materials. This persistent concern necessitates a focused investigation into how effective management of instructional materials can enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State.

Statement of the Problem

The persistent decline and inconsistency in students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State have raised serious concerns among educators, parents, and policymakers. Despite the provision of instructional materials by the government and other stakeholders, evidence from many schools suggests that these resources are either poorly organised, inadequately utilised, or rarely evaluated for effectiveness. In some cases, instructional materials are kept in storage without proper cataloguing, making them difficult for teachers to access when needed. This poor organisation disrupts lesson planning and limits the integration of relevant teaching aids that could enhance students' understanding of complex concepts. Consequently, teaching often becomes overly theoretical, reducing students' engagement and lowering the quality of learning outcomes.

Furthermore, even where instructional materials are available, many teachers do not utilise them effectively due to a lack of training, time constraints, or negative attitudes towards innovative teaching methods. This underutilisation denies students the opportunity to experience interactive and practical learning that could improve retention and academic performance. In addition, the absence of regular evaluation of these materials creates uncertainty about their relevance, adequacy, and alignment with curriculum objectives. Outdated, damaged, or inappropriate materials may continue to be used without

assessment of their impact on students' learning. These issues collectively point to a critical management gap in the organisation, utilisation, and evaluation of instructional materials, which may be contributing significantly to the unsatisfactory academic achievement observed among students in public secondary schools in Abia State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to examine instructional materials organisation, utilisation and evaluation for students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State. Specifically, the objectives of the study sought to;

1. ascertain ways instructional materials are organised to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State.
2. examine ways instructional materials are utilised to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State.
3. identify ways instructional materials are evaluated to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the ways instructional materials are organised to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State?
2. In what ways are instructional materials utilised to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State?
3. What are the ways instructional materials are evaluated to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses of the study were tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female teachers on the ways instructional materials are organised to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of urban and rural teachers on the ways instructional materials are utilised to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female teachers on the ways instructional materials are evaluated to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive research design to investigate how teachers manage available instructional materials to improve students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Abia State. The population comprised 2,074 teachers from 252 schools, from which a sample of 335 was determined using Taro Yamane's formula and selected through stratified random sampling across the three senatorial districts to ensure proper representation. Data were gathered using a structured instrument titled: Instructional Materials Organisation, Utilisation and Evaluation for Students' Academic Achievement Questionnaire (IMOUESAAQ), which addressed planning, acquisition, organisation, utilisation, and evaluation of instructional materials on a 4-point Likert scale. The instrument was validated by experts in Measurement and Evaluation, while its reliability was established using Cronbach's alpha coefficients ranging from 0.79 to 0.89, yielding an overall reliability index of 0.81. With the support of trained research assistants, the questionnaire was administered and 317 copies were successfully retrieved, representing a 95% return rate. Data analysis involved the use of mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while the hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance using the z-test, with a criterion mean of 2.50 for decision-making.

RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Research Question 1: *What are the ways instructional materials are organised to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State?*

Table 1: Mean (\bar{x}) and Standard Deviation of Respondents (Teachers) on the Ways Instructional Materials are Organised to Enhance Students' Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools in Abia State

SN	Items	Male N = 146		Female N = 171		Mean Set $\frac{x_1x_2}{2}$	Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂		
1.	The school has a dedicated storage system for instructional materials.	1.91	0.17	1.95	0.14	1.93	Disagree
2.	Instructional materials are properly labeled and categorised by subject.	1.90	0.15	1.97	0.18	1.94	Disagree
3.	Teachers are trained on how to organise instructional materials for easy access	2.22	0.21	2.14	0.20	2.18	Disagree
4.	Materials are stored in a centralised location.	2.51	0.41	2.71	0.86	2.61	Agree
5.	There is a teacher responsible for the management of instructional materials in my school.	1.95	0.14	1.92	0.13	1.94	Disagree
6.	A timetable/logbook is maintained for issuing and returning materials.	2.11	0.18	2.10	0.17	2.11	Disagree
7.	Instructional materials are updated regularly.	2.21	0.20	2.15	0.17	2.18	Disagree
8.	The organisation of instructional materials allows for easy integration into lesson plans.	3.16	1.08	3.10	1.02	3.13	Agree
9.	Students have controlled access to some instructional materials.	2.13	0.12	2.18	0.15	2.16	Disagree
10.	Digital instructional materials are stored systematically for use.	2.19	0.16	2.15	0.13	2.17	Disagree
Average Mean/Standard Deviation		2.23	0.28	2.24	0.32	2.24	Disagree

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2025.

Data in Table 1 showed that items 4 and 8 had mean rating scores above the criterion mean of 2.50 and were agreed as the ways instructional materials are organised to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State, because their mean set scores were higher than the criterion mean of 2.50. Contrarily, items 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 9 and 10 had mean set scores below the criterion mean of 2.50, and this shows that the respondents disagreed on those items as the ways instructional materials are organised to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State.

In summary, from Table 1, both female and male teachers agree that the ways instructional materials are organised to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State include: materials are stored in a centralised location, and the organisation of instructional materials allows for easy integration into the lesson plan

Research Question 2: *In what ways are instructional materials utilised to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State?*

Table 2: Mean (\bar{x}) and Standard Deviation of Respondents (Teachers) on the Ways Instructional Materials are Utilised to Enhance Students' Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools in Abia State

SN	Items	Urban N = 203		Rural N = 114		Mean Set $\frac{x_1x_2}{2}$	Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂		
11.	Teachers use instructional materials regularly during teaching.	2.12	0.14	2.01	0.10	2.07	Disagree
12.	Teachers incorporate instructional materials into their lesson plans.	2.71	0.81	2.67	0.58	2.69	Agree
13.	Teachers adapt materials to suit the learning levels of their students.	2.59	0.53	2.57	0.51	2.58	Agree
14.	Varieties of instructional materials (e.g., charts, models, videos, real objects).	2.16	0.18	2.18	0.19	2.17	Disagree
15.	Students are allowed to interact with instructional materials during lessons.	2.28	0.26	2.42	0.33	2.35	Disagree
16.	Teachers evaluate the effectiveness of materials after each lesson.	2.51	0.47	2.49	0.45	2.50	Agree
17.	Digital materials (e.g., PowerPoint, videos) are frequently used by teachers in teaching.	2.11	0.13	2.00	0.10	2.06	Disagree
18.	Teachers utilise instructional materials to explain abstract or complex concepts.	2.56	0.50	2.51	0.47	2.54	Agree
19.	Instructional materials are used across all subjects in the school.	2.13	0.16	2.33	0.25	2.23	Disagree
20.	Teachers encourage students to create and use their own instructional materials.	2.61	0.62	2.72	0.73	2.67	Agree
Average Mean/Standard Deviation		2.38	0.38	2.39	0.37	2.39	Disagree

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2025.

Data in Table 2 showed that items 12, 13, 16, 18 and 20 had mean rating scores above the criterion mean of 2.50 and this shows that the respondents agree on those items as the ways instructional materials are utilised to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State, because their mean set scores were higher than the criterion mean of 2.50. On the other hand, items 11, 14, 15, 17 and 19 had mean set scores below the criterion mean of 2.50, and this shows that the respondents disagree on those items as the ways instructional materials are utilized to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State.

In summary, from Table 2, both urban and rural teachers agree that the ways instructional materials are acquired to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State include: teachers incorporate instructional materials into their lesson plans, teachers adapt materials to suit the learning levels of their students, teachers evaluate the effectiveness of materials after each lesson, teachers utilise instructional materials to explain abstract or complex concepts, and teachers encourage students to create and use their own instructional materials.

Research Question 3: *What are the ways instructional materials are evaluated to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State?*

Table 3: Mean (\bar{x}) and Standard Deviation of Respondents (Teachers) on the Ways Instructional Materials are Evaluated to Enhance Students' Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools in Abia State

SN	Items	Male N = 146		Female N = 171		Mean Set $\frac{x_1x_2}{2}$	Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂		
21.	Instructional materials used in this school are regularly evaluated for effectiveness.	1.95	0.21	1.65	0.12	1.80	Disagree
22.	There is a formal process in place for assessing the quality of instructional materials.	1.90	0.15	1.77	0.15	1.84	Disagree
23.	Evaluation of instructional materials is based on curriculum relevance.	2.12	0.20	2.14	0.22	2.13	Disagree
24.	Instructional materials are assessed for alignment with students' learning outcomes.	2.11	0.19	2.01	0.10	2.06	Disagree
25.	Student performance data is used to evaluate the effectiveness of instructional materials.	2.53	0.42	2.61	0.66	2.57	Agree
26.	The cultural appropriateness of materials is considered during evaluation.	2.51	0.51	2.60	0.69	2.56	Agree
27.	The readability and language level of materials are suitable for the target students.	2.61	0.65	2.55	0.47	2.58	Agree
28.	Instructional materials are evaluated for their ability to promote critical thinking and problem-solving.	2.66	0.69	2.47	0.38	2.57	Agree
29.	The visual and design quality of materials is assessed during evaluation.	2.13	0.12	2.18	0.15	2.16	Disagree
30.	External education experts are sometimes consulted in the evaluation process.	2.15	0.23	2.10	0.20	2.13	Disagree
Average Mean/Standard Deviation		2.27	0.34	2.21	0.31	2.24	Disagree

Source: Researcher's Field Result, 2025.

Data in Table 3 showed that items 25, 26, 27 and 28 had mean rating scores above the criterion mean of 2.50 and this shows that the respondents agree on those items as the ways instructional materials are evaluated to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State, because their mean set scores were higher than the criterion mean of 2.50. On the other hand, item 21, 22, 23, 24, 29 and 30 had mean set scores below the criterion mean of 2.50, and this shows that the respondents disagree on those items as the ways instructional materials are utilized to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State.

In summary, from Table 3, both male and female teachers agree that the ways instructional materials are evaluated to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State include: student performance data is used to evaluate the effectiveness of instructional materials, the cultural appropriateness of materials is considered during evaluation, the readability and language level of materials are suitable for the target students, and instructional materials are evaluated for their ability to promote critical thinking and problem-solving.

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis One (Ho₁): There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the ways instructional materials are organised to enhance students’ academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State.

Table 4: Summary of z-test Analysis of the Difference between the Mean Scores of Male and Female Teachers on the Ways Instructional Materials are Organised to Enhance Students’ Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools in Abia State

Variable	N	\bar{x}	SD	df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Level of Significance	Decision
Male	146	2.23	0.28					Ho ₁ Accepted
				315	-0.30	-1.96	0.05	(Not Significant)
Famale	171	2.24	0.32					

Data on Table 4 shows the value of z-cal. to be -0.30 while the value of z-crit. was -1.96. Since the value of z-cal. of -0.30 is less than the values of z-crit. of 1.96, the null hypothesis (Ho₁) was accepted and this implied that no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the ways instructional materials are organised to enhance students’ academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State.

Hypothesis Two (Ho₂): There is no significant difference between the mean scores of urban and rural teachers on the ways instructional materials are utilised to enhance students’ academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State.

Table 5: Summary of z-test Analysis of the Difference between the Mean Scores of Male and Female Teachers on the Ways Instructional Materials are Utilised to Enhance Students’ Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools in Abia State

Variable	N	\bar{x}	SD	df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Level of Significance	Decision
Urban	203	2.38	0.38					Ho ₂
				315	-0.23	-1.96	0.05	(Not Significant)
Rural	114	2.39	0.37					

Data in Table 5 shows the value of z-cal. to be -0.23 while the value of z-crit. was 1.96. Since the value of z-cal. of -0.23 is less than the values of z-crit. of 1.96, the null hypothesis (Ho₂) was accepted and this implied that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of urban and rural teachers on the ways instructional materials are utilised to enhance students’ academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State.

Hypothesis Three (Ho₃): There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the ways instructional materials are evaluated to enhance students’ academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State.

Table 6: Summary of z-test Analysis of the Difference between the Mean Scores of Male and Female Teachers on the Ways Instructional Materials are Evaluated to Enhance Students' Academic Achievement in Public Secondary Schools in Abia State

Variable	N	\bar{x}	SD	df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Level of Significance	Decision
Male	146	2.27	0.34					Ho ₃ Accepted
				315	1.60	1.96	0.05	(Not Significant)
Famale	171	2.21	0.31					

Data in Table 6 shows the value of z-cal. to be 1.60 while the value of z-crit. was 1.96. Since the value of z-cal. of 1.60 is less than the values of z-crit. of 1.96, the null hypothesis (Ho₃) was accepted and this implied that there was no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the ways instructional materials are evaluated to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first finding of the study showed that the ways instructional materials are organised to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State include: materials are stored in a centralised location, and the organisation of instructional materials allows for easy integration into lesson plans. Also, a corresponding finding from a test of hypothesis establishes no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the ways instructional materials are organised to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State. These findings agree with Ajayi and Fadekemi (2020), Hilton (2021), Umo and Eze (2021), Onuka and Samuel (2022), and Uche and Ibrahim (2023), whose empirical and scholarly contributions to knowledge attest to the ways identified. A possible explanation for these findings suggests that centralised storage and structured organisation of instructional materials facilitate teachers' access and integration into lesson plans, enhancing instructional delivery. The absence of a significant gender difference implies a uniform approach among male and female teachers in organising materials to support student achievement. The findings indicate that efficient organisation and centralised storage of instructional materials support effective lesson planning and accessibility for all teachers. The lack of gender disparity suggests that training and organisational practices are equally adopted by both male and female teachers, promoting consistency in instructional delivery.

The second finding of the study revealed that the ways instructional materials are utilised to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State include: teachers incorporate instructional materials into their lesson plans, teachers adapt materials to suit the learning levels of their students, teachers evaluate the effectiveness of materials after each lesson, teachers utilise instructional materials to explain abstract or complex concepts, and teachers encourage students to create and use their instructional materials. Also, a corresponding finding from hypothesis testing establishes that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of urban and rural teachers on the ways instructional materials are utilised to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State. These findings agree with Olanrewaju and Musa (2021), Tamim et al. (2021), Afolabi and Adewale (2022), Okon and Adesina (2022), Uche and Ibrahim (2023), and Nwachukwu and Ugwu (2023), whose comments and research findings present information on the ways instructional materials are utilised in schools. A possible explanation for these findings suggests that teachers in Abia State actively engage with instructional materials by tailoring them to student needs, integrating them into lesson delivery, and evaluating their effectiveness. These practices likely contribute to improved comprehension, especially of abstract concepts, and promote student creativity and involvement. The lack of significant difference

between urban and rural teachers implies a uniform approach to instructional material utilisation across school locations. Nevertheless, the findings imply that effective utilisation of instructional materials is a common and essential strategy among teachers across both urban and rural schools in Abia State, fostering inclusive and enhanced learning experiences. This uniformity suggests that professional development efforts in material use are yielding consistent practices regardless of school location.

The third finding of the study showed that the ways instructional materials are evaluated to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State include: student performance data is used to evaluate the effectiveness of instructional materials, the cultural appropriateness of materials is considered during evaluation, the readability and language level of materials are suitable for the target students, and instructional materials are evaluated for their ability to promote critical thinking and problem-solving. Also, a corresponding finding from test of hypothesis establishes that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the ways instructional materials are evaluated to enhance students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State. These findings agree with Ogunleye and Dada (2021), Ojo and Alade (2022), Nwachukwu and Obasi (2022), Adeyemo and Omotayo (2022), and Eze and Chukwu (2023). These scholars and researchers, in their scholarly contributions, establish that the identified variables are the ways for evaluating instructional materials in schools.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the study concludes that effective organisation, utilisation, and evaluation of instructional materials significantly contribute to students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Abia State, while gender differences among teachers showed no significant impact.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The Ministry of Education should develop and enforce a uniform system for organising instructional materials in schools to improve accessibility and instructional efficiency.
2. The government, through the Ministry of Education, should encourage collaborative teaching strategies, where teachers from diverse locations share techniques for effective and equitable material utilisation practices, to curb urban-rural differences in the utilization of materials.
3. The government should regularly organise workshops and provide tools to help all teachers improve their evaluation skills to ensure instructional effectiveness and student-centered learning.

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